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Real-time tracking system for medical devices and equipment

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Summary

This thesis refers to the development of a real-time tracking system for medical devices and equipment within hospital units. It starts by highlighting its main purpose, which is to improve the quality of healthcare, make more efficient use of medical equipment and address malfunctions affecting patient care.

Then, after defining the localisation system, the various technologies with which it can be implemented are analysed and its basic structure is presented. The applications of such a system both in healthcare and other sectors are also highlighted, but the challenges and limitations it faces are also mentioned. The wider use of technology in healthcare and patient care and the new perspectives it offers are also presented.

In the chapter that analyses the design of the system, reference is made to the issues it solves and the capabilities it provides to its users. In addition, it describes the architecture of the system and the components used to build it, and details the implementation process.

In the next chapter, the experimental test conducted to evaluate the tracking system is described and all scenarios and possible conditions are considered. Then, the measurement results are analyzed in two phases. The first one is a simple comparison of the data, which leads to a general evaluation of the system, while the second one provides more reliability and objectivity, since it includes the statistical methods T-Test, ANOVA test and confidence interval.

Finally, the performance of the system is evaluated by drawing well-founded conclusions. At the same time, possible future extensions are explored, which could contribute to the further development and expansion of its capabilities.

Key words: Real-time tracking system, Wi-Fi, hospital, healthcare, medical devices

Περίληψη

Η παρούσα διπλωματική εργασία αναφέρεται στην ανάπτυξη ενός συστήματος εντοπισμού ιατρικών συσκευών και εξοπλισμού σε πραγματικό χρόνο εντός νοσοκομειακών μονάδων. Αρχικά επισημαίνεται ο βασικός σκοπός του, ο οποίος είναι η βελτίωση της ποιότητας υγειονομικής περίθαλψης, η αποδοτικότερη χρήση ιατρικών μηχανημάτων και η αντιμετώπιση δυσλειτουργιών που επηρεάζουν τη φροντίδα των ασθενών.

Στη συνέχεια, αφού δοθεί ο ορισμός του συστήματος εντοπισμού, αναλύονται οι διάφορες τεχνολογίες με τις οποίες μπορεί να υλοποιηθεί και παρατίθεται η βασική δομή του. Επισημαίνονται ακόμα οι εφαρμογές ενός τέτοιου συστήματος τόσο στον τομέα της υγειονομικής περίθαλψης όσο και σε άλλους κλάδους αλλά γίνεται και αναφορά στις προκλήσεις και τους περιορισμούς που αντιμετωπίζει. Επίσης, παρουσιάζεται η ευρύτερη χρήση της τεχνολογίας στον τομέα της Υγείας και της φροντίδας του ασθενή και οι νέες προοπτικές που προσφέρει.

Στο κεφάλαιο που αναλύει τον σχεδιασμό του συστήματος, γίνεται αναφορά στα ζητήματα που επιλύει και στις δυνατότητες που παρέχει στους χρήστες του. Επιπλέον, αποτυπώνεται η αρχιτεκτονική του συστήματος και τα εξαρτήματα που χρησιμοποιήθηκαν για την κατασκευή του αλλά γίνεται και λεπτομερής παρουσίαση της διαδικασίας υλοποίησής του.

Στο επόμενο κεφάλαιο, περιγράφεται η πειραματική δοκιμή που πραγματοποιήθηκε για να αξιολογηθεί το σύστημα εντοπισμού και εξετάζονται όλες τα σενάρια και οι πιθανές συνθήκες. Έπειτα, αναλύονται τα αποτελέσματα των μετρήσεων σε δύο φάσεις. Η πρώτη αποτελεί μια απλή σύγκριση των δεδομένων, η οποία οδηγεί σε μια γενική αξιολόγηση του συστήματος, ενώ η δεύτερη παρέχει μεγαλύτερη αξιοπιστία και αντικειμενικότητα, από τη στιγμή που περιλαμβάνει τις στατιστικές μεθόδους T-Test, ANOVA test και το διάστημα εμπιστοσύνης.

Τέλος, πραγματοποιείται η αποτίμηση της απόδοσης του συστήματος μέσω της εξαγωγής τεκμηριωμένων συμπερασμάτων. Παράλληλα, διερευνώνται πιθανές μελλοντικές επεκτάσεις, οι οποίες θα μπορούσαν να συμβάλουν στην περαιτέρω εξέλιξη και διεύρυνση των δυνατοτήτων του.

Λέξεις κλειδιά: Σύστημα εντοπισμού σε πραγματικό χρόνο, Wi-Fi, νοσοκομείο, υγειονομική περίθαλψη, ιατρικές συσκευές

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1 Introduction

1.1 Choice of subject

The choice of the topic of the thesis arose from a personal interest in Internet of Things (IoT) applications in the field of Medicine and Health and from the observation of the daily operation of hospital premises and especially of patient rooms. The supervisor of the thesis, Mr. Asvestas Pantelis, contributed to this topic, who with his valuable ideas and guidance contributed to the deepening in the field of device tracking systems.

1.2 Purpose

The aim of this thesis is the construction of a real-time tracking system for medical devices and equipment within a hospital unit in order to improve the quality of patient healthcare and to make the use of medical equipment faster and more effective in emergency situations.

1.3 Importance of locating medical devices

The real-time tracking of medical devices within the hospital or clinic is vital because it is driven by the wider evolution and upgrading of the way hospitals operate and provide patient care[1]. Initially, with the installation of this system, the provision of services to the patient will be significantly improved. Nursing staff spends valuable time searching for machines or devices during the shift, time that could be dedicated to further patient care[2]. In an emergency situation where the use of a device is required to be done within a few seconds, its immediate location can save a human life[1]. In addition, nurses are responsible for both transporting medical devices between nursing rooms and communicating their location to other staff[3]. The medical equipment tracking system offers the possibility of updating any failure of medical equipment and in this way it is perceived that it will be repaired more immediately, thus reducing maintenance costs[1]. By recording and storing the movement history of each machine within the hospital unit, the most frequently used equipment in a given period of time can be viewed. This is clearly necessary as management staff will make purchases and investments based on the needs of each unit.[2]

1.4 Healthcare industry

The healthcare sector is undoubtedly one of the fastest growing in the last two decades in modern society. This is confirmed by its market value, which already in 2015 in the United States amounted to tens of trillions of dollars. This amount translates into 14.3 million new jobs that had been created by 2008 and also 3.2 million by 2018[2]. As for the medical device management market, its value was estimated at \$6.7 billion in 2015 and \$29.6 billion in 2020.

In the period 1998-2006, the costs of purchasing medical equipment and medical devices increased from \$145 billion to \$220 billion worldwide[2]. It is therefore clear that the above amounts and numbers have increased even more to date, which makes the tracking of medical devices even more useful and essential.

General Electric's Healthcare Asset Management division conducted two surveys between 1995-1997 and 2008-2010 respectively, aiming to highlight the importance of locating medical equipment. Taking data from 45 different hospitals in the United States, they published the results which were related to 3 categories. Specifically, over the period of these 15 years, the average cost of repair per medical device showed an increase of \$40 as it went from \$210 to \$250. In addition, the number of devices required to treat a patient increased from 8 to 13. Finally, the average cost of repair and maintenance of removable devices per bed had the greatest rate of change because it increased from \$1656 to \$3144, which translates to an estimated 90% increase[2] . The three categories of statistics reported are graphically presented in Figure 1, Figure 2 and Figure 3 respectively.

Figure 1. Average maintenance costs per device between 1995-1997 and 2008-2010 (dollars) [2]

Figure 2. Number of devices required per patient in the periods 1995-1997 and 2008-2010 [2]

Figure 3. Average cost of appliance repair per bed between 1995-1997 and [2]

2 Literature review

This chapter analyses the theoretical background on which this paper is based. First, the definition of a positioning system is given and its three main categories are listed. Then, the technologies with which such a system can be built are detailed and a comparison between them is made based on their advantages and disadvantages in a detailed table. Its basic structure and the components of which it is composed are described and the process of transferring the location data and the way in which it is displayed to the end user are explained. Also, the applications of a positioning system in both the health care sector and other sectors such as industrial, livestock and large scale sites such as airports are mentioned. Finally, after highlighting the limitations of such a system, the broader use of technology in healthcare and how it offers new possibilities and perspectives in modern society is discussed.

2.1 Definition of localisation system

The term tracking system refers to the technology of determining the location of an object within a site of interest[4] . Various types of sensors receive data and then, after analysis, project the location in a two- or three-dimensional plane .[5]

Such a system is divided into the following three (3) categories: Global Positioning System-GPS, Local Positioning System-LPS, and Hybrid Positioning System-HPS, which is a combination of GPS and LPS[4] . The Global Positioning System (GPS) is based on satellites placed around the Earth and has applications in areas such as mapping, weather forecasting, the military, and the distribution of goods and products[4] . In contrast, Local Positioning System (LPS) works based on specific devices placed inside buildings such as a hospital or medical center, a factory, an airport or even a house.

2.2 Positioning system technologies

A positioning system can be built with various technologies based on the requirements of each case and the capabilities offered by each site. The different categories into which it is divided are discussed below and are presented in summary in Figure 4. Figure 5 highlights the advantages and disadvantages of each technology, making a comparison between the systems.

2.2.1 Satellite positioning system

These Global Positioning System (GPS) systems rely on satellite signals transmitted by satellites placed in the upper atmospheric layers of the Earth. In 95% of cases, their error is less than 7.8 metres. They are only applicable outdoors where satellite signal reception is stable and structures and buildings do not interfere[4] . Therefore, their use indoors is not preferred as the signal is weakened and becomes inaccurate.

2.2.2 Magnetic positioning system

Such a system can work in two main ways. The first is based on measuring values of the Earth's magnetic field at various points, usually using a magnetometer. The object of interest is given a magnetic field value and its position is determined by comparing this value with those recorded

by the magnetometer at a previous stage. This method is also known as fingerprinting[6] as a map of "fingerprints" is created with measurements at predetermined locations, which are compared with the real-time measurements. The second method relies on measuring the magnetic field artificially emitted by devices placed indoors. The location in space is determined by measuring the strength of the emitted magnetic field .[4]

2.2.3 System based on inertial sensors

There are positioning systems that do not depend on external signals from other sources but are autonomous. Their basic principle is Newton's First Law (Law of Inertia), according to which an object remains at rest or moves at a constant speed in a straight line unless acted upon by an external force. The operation of these systems is based on special inertial sensors such as accelerometers and gyroscopes. The first instruments measure the acceleration of an object due to external forces or gravity, thus providing information about the object's movement in the Cartesian coordinate system[6] . Gyroscopes, on the other hand, calculate the rotational movement of the object (angular velocity) and thus the change of orientation is known. Both types of sensors are embedded in the object of interest or the person whose location is being tracked and transmit the data to a central computer .[4]

2.2.4 Sound-based positioning system

Positioning systems based on the transmission of sound waves have a significant advantage over those using electromagnetic waves. The speed of sound waves in the air is higher than that of electromagnetic waves, which helps to make it easier to calculate the difference between the transmission time and the reception time of the sound wave[6] . The first category of these systems is based on the use of acoustic sound, i.e. the sound perceived by humans (20Hz to 20kHz). The object or person whose position in space is to be detected carries a special microphone that picks up the sound produced by its surrounding environment. The technique of producing an artificial sound is not often applied as it causes a constant disturbance to people in close proximity [6] . For this reason, a different technique is used where a sonic watermark is added to sounds that already exist in specific spaces such as music in a shopping mall or an outdoor area[6] . The sonic watermark is sound that is embedded in the already existing sound and offers the advantage of not being recognized by the human ear. Thus the microphone receives the processed sounds from the surrounding environment and from their analysis, the location of the object of interest or person is estimated[7] . The second category of systems based on sound for positioning are ultrasound systems, which can be active or passive[6] . In particular, sound waves are used which are not perceived by humans, i.e. they exceed the frequency of 20 kHz. The location of the object of interest is obtained by calculating the time it takes for an ultrasonic wave to travel from the transmitter to the receiver[4] . The third and final category is acoustic sound systems, which are not limited to a specific frequency range but use the entire range of sound waves. To find the location of an object or person, techniques such as the calculation of the angle of incidence of the sound wave on the sensor, the time required for the sound wave to reach the sensor, the time difference of arrival of a sound wave between two different points and the difference of the arrival frequency of a sound wave between two different points are used . [4]

2.2.5 Optical positioning system

An optical positioning system uses optical signals, a type of electromagnetic radiation. It is divided into those based on infrared light and visible light[4] . The former use as basic structures, a photodiode that emits infrared light in the form of a signal and a second photodiode that receives the emitted signal[6] . From this, and usually by calculating the angle of incidence of the signal, the position of the object of interest in space is detected[4] . On the other hand, a positioning system using the visible spectrum of radiation has a different approach, as it uses the light already present in a space. Specifically, light sources such as Light-Emitting Diode-LEDs or any other modern light bulbs are coded in such a way that they flash at a specific frequency that is not perceived by the human eye[6] . This rapid change in the light state of each bulb is detected by a sensor carried by the object of interest or a person. The sensor can be a photodiode, a camera or a photocell. Thus, from the light power received from each source, it calculates which one it is closest to and thus the position in space is determined in this way .[6]

2.2.6 Position tracking system based on image recording

Such a system locates the position of an object or person in space based on the recorded image from various cameras[6] . The first method involves recording motion of the object of interest from cameras installed at specific points in space. By analyzing the characteristics of the image provided by the cameras in a centralized system, the position in space is estimated[4] . The second method is based on the image recorded by a camera, which is carried by the object or person whose location is being monitored. The camera data is transferred to a central system where the recorded images are compared with images already stored in it and corresponding to a specific location in space. In this way the algorithm decides at which coordinates the object of interest is located depending on the similarity of the images[6]

2.2.7 Radio frequency positioning system

The first category of radio-frequency positioning system is one that uses the radio frequency spectrum (20kHz to 300 GHz) and provides accuracy up to 0.5 meter (Radio-frequency identification-RFID)[4] . It consists of RFID tags, RFID receivers and a central computer system that processes the data. The principle of this system is based on the fact that each tag emits a separate radio signal, which corresponds to its identity, i.e. leads to its identification by the receivers. Its operation is based on the way in which the specific tags interact with the receivers. When they have a passive role, they do not involve any kind of battery. The receivers emit a small electrical signal, the energy of which the passive tags use to relay their identity and carry the required information back to the receivers[6] . In the case where the tags have an active role, they have an independent power supply, i.e. a built-in battery. Therefore, they continuously emit a signal, which is received by the receivers located in the[6] space. However, there are also semi-active tags, which, although they carry a small battery, emit a signal only when they are perceived to be in close proximity to a receiver[6] . As for the installation of the structures of this system, there are two alternatives. In the first, the object of interest or the person whose location is detected carries a tag, whose signal is picked up by the receivers in the area. In the second case, the object or person carries a radio receiver, which receives signals from multiple tags embedded in the surrounding area[6] . One realizes that the former is more commonly applied due to the volume

of RFID receivers. Finally, there is NFC technology which is a subset of RFID. It is a way for devices to communicate and if they are within a few centimeters of each other, they exchange data essentially intact[6] . So this method can also be applied to locate devices in space.

The second main category of system that uses radio frequencies is the one based on the Wi-Fi local area network. It is mainly used indoors such as offices, homes, hotels and medical centres[8] . It offers an accuracy of 5-15 meters, has a high power consumption and the signal is often affected by the wall material and other Wi-Fi devices in the room[4] . Its main element is the presence of several Wi-Fi access points in the room where the object of interest is located[8] . Wi-Fi access points create their own network and allow devices to connect wirelessly to them. Two techniques are predominant for locating an object or person in the space. The first one uses the Received Signal Strength Indicator-RSSI (Received Signal Strength Indicator) from each access point and based on the triangulation method, the location in space is detected. Triangulation is a mathematical method where a different circle is drawn for three separate access points and the object of interest corresponds to the intersection of the three rays[9] . The larger the RSSI, the larger the size of each circle. The second technique involves recording the received Wi-Fi signal power index values at multiple points in space and storing them in a database. Then, the values received by the device carried by the individual are compared with the existing values from the database and thus the coordinates in the space[6] are calculated. This technique is called fingerprinting as mentioned earlier.

The third category of tracking system that uses the radio frequency spectrum is that of Bluetooth technology, which operates in the 2.4 to 2.48 GHz frequency range[10] . It is mainly used indoors as it is ideal for data transfer between short distances and its accuracy ranges from 2 to 3 meters[6] . Its basic function relies on the transfer of data between mobile devices or between mobile devices and devices installed at specific points in space[6] . A modern mobile phone (smartphone) or any other device that supports Bluetooth technology is used as a mobile device, while small devices called beacons are placed on walls[4] . Beacons have a built-in battery and continuously transmit their signal to the smartphone, which in turn receives the signal and transmits it to a central system. In it, based on the signal strength received by the smartphone from each beacon, the data is processed and the location of the person carrying the smartphone is calculated[6] . The power consumption of the beacons is very low and the battery can be replaced after several months or even years[6] . So for this reason, this technology is known as Bluetooth Low Energy-BLE (Bluetooth Low Energy-BLE).

The fourth and final category is Ultrawideband technology (UWB). It is applied in large-scale security systems, radar systems and device tracking systems[6] . It uses a much wider frequency range than the previous technologies, which leads to the transfer of larger volumes of data with lower power consumption[4] . It works on the basis of UWB transmitters (tags) and special sensors that receive the transmitted signal from the transmitters. This signal is of low frequency and thus walls and other structures do not prevent its transmission through them[4] . The calculation of the position of the object of interest is done by measuring the time the signal reaches the sensor (Time of Arrival ToA), the difference in the time of arrival of the signal from different transmitters (tags) and also the fingerprinting technique as has been analyzed previously[6] . The UWB technique provides the best accuracy, which ranges from 0.1 to 0.3 meters in position in space

and has very low power consumption. This makes it the most widely used technology in recent years although the installation of a UWB system is expensive[8]

Figure 4 . Technologies of indoor positioning systems [4]

Technologies	Advantages	Disadvantages
Satellite-Based	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GPS easy to navigate • Low-cost implementation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cannot be implemented in an indoor environment • Less accurate
Magnetic-Based	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High accuracy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High-cost implementation • Complex
Inertial-Based	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High accuracy • Wide range application • Does not require hardware installation • High accuracy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fused with magnetic to get long-term stabilization • Complex
Sound-Based		
Audible Sound	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less expensive • Easy to implement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High-cost implementation
Ultrasonic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Close range distance measurement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High-cost implementation
Acoustic sound	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low-cost implementation • Easy to implement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complex
Optical-Based	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low-cost implementation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complex • Low accuracy
Radio Frequency (RF)-Based		
Wi-Fi	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low-cost implementation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High power consumption
BLE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low power consumption • High accuracy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complex • High-cost implementation
RFID	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small size • High accuracy • Low power consumption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High-cost implementation • Complex
UWB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High-in accuracy • Low power consumption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High-cost implementation
Vision-Based	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low-cost implementation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low accuracy • Complex

Figure 5. Comparison of system technologies [4]

2.3 Structure of a positioning system

A real-time positioning system of an object of interest consists of 4 different structures, which are: tags, specific sensors, a central location calculation software and a user interaction software[11]. It is important to note that these two pieces of software are not always located on different electronic devices, but can often coexist on one computer[12]. Signal transmitters, or tags, are embedded in the device of interest and each emits a unique signal proportional to the technology used[12]. The devices of interest can be ventilators, portable defibrillators, portable ultrasound and radiology machines and even entire electrically powered patient beds. Special sensors placed at various points in the environment receive the signals from the transmitters and in turn transmit them to the central software. The latter, after processing the data coming from the sensors, calculates the location of the object of interest in the space and transmits the

information to the next software. The final software is connected to various applications, which it uses to display the location of the object in space. Through the applications, the user tracks the location of the object of interest and other information about it, such as its movement history[12]. In Figure 6 the structure of such a system is shown to make it more understandable.

Figure 6. General impression of the structure of a tracking system [11]

The position of the medical device can be displayed in various ways, depending on the requirements of each room and the users. A common case is for the system to display whether or not the device of interest is located within certain boundaries, such as for example within the boundaries of the intensive care unit. The location can also be presented to the user at the room level - that is, in which room of the site the device is located - but also by the exact location within it when more detail is required. In addition, the view of the location in the space can be performed in relation to a specific point in the space. For example, a sensor is placed at the entrance of a bed and is activated by the signal of the transmitter (tag) carried by the device of interest each time it passes through the door of the room. Thus the tracking system in this case notifies the end user of the entry or exit of a device from a room. Another way of projecting the location in space is based on the coordinates of the object of interest in relation to another object in the environment or person, which also carries a signal transmitter (tag). In particular, the end user is shown how close the first object is to the second. Finally, in areas where great precision and detail about the location of devices is required, their location is displayed with their exact coordinates in the[12] space.

2.4 Implementation of a tracking system in the healthcare sector

A real-time tracking system can be used to record the location of various medical devices and equipment as well as people such as medical and nursing staff or patients themselves. As far as the location of a person in space is concerned, a tracking system can be used in patients suffering from Alzheimer's disease[12] . This disease is incurable, causing short-term memory loss, confusion with space and motor difficulties in later stages. For this reason, therefore, the movement and location of these patients is tracked to keep them within the confines of the clinic[12] . Another case, is that of monitoring the movement of patients between medical units in a hospital. For example, knowing how often patients are moved from the emergency room to the radiology unit can provide useful information on the need to purchase further equipment or even hire new staff[12] . Finally, due to the fact that in several psychiatric clinics there are incidents of patients attacking medical staff, a tracking system for emergencies can be implemented ref. Each nurse is equipped with a signal transmitter (tag), which has a built-in

switch that immediately alerts for help and advances the location to the site in case of verbal or physical assault by a patient[12] . Regarding the tracking of medical devices and medical equipment, a similar system can be applied to machines such as vital signs monitor, mobile electrocardiograph, portable ventilator and equipment such as wheelchair and electric patient lifting crane. In emergencies where the patient requires immediate intervention, the tracking system reduces the time needed to search for devices, which can become vital in several cases. In addition, location tracking can be applied to high-cost machines such as portable ultrasound or portable blood analyzers to prevent them from being stolen or damaged .[12]

2.5 Implementation of a tracking system in other sectors

Beyond the healthcare sector, a tracking system can also be used in sectors such as the industrial sector. In large warehouses, tracking the progress and movement of products within them offers efficiency in their management as their availability is updated live and potential losses are reduced. Moreover, in the same environment where high volume loads are carried by workers, a tracking system can contribute to their safety and prevent any accidents. Location awareness is also essential in the air transport sector. Tags can be integrated into each piece of luggage and their location transmitted to a central monitoring system in order to reduce incidents of loss or damage and even reduce the time needed to collect them after a journey. Finally, a tracking system can also be applied in the livestock sector to record the location of each individual animal. This will help to monitor the daily behaviour of the animal (grazing and resting time), to detect any disease using special sensors embedded in the tags and to automatically count the herd .[13]

2.6 Challenges and constraints

The development and implementation of an indoor tracking system faces significant challenges, which negatively affect its overall effectiveness and at the same time its reliability. One of the most important problems is signal attenuation. The same is caused both by the absence of clear line of sight between the transmitter and receiver due to physical obstacles such as bulky machinery and also due to the peculiarity of the space[14] . The interruption of the signal path by various obstacles and its reflection on the walls of the rooms results in incorrect signal value being received by the system sensors[14] . Thus, the position of the object of interest is calculated inaccurately and leads to an incorrect projection of the object of interest to the end user. TheFigure 7 shows the signal attenuation due to each different material of construction and the attenuation factor. As it approaches 0, the more the signal absorption of the material increases, while as it approaches the value1, it means that the attenuation decreases and most of the signal passes through the material[15] . Still, the difficulty and cost of installing a tracking system constitutes a major limitation. Placing a large number of sensors and complex structures within a hospital, for example, requires a lot of time and high financial costs for the administration. Replacing the batteries of the signal transmitters (tags) is also something that certainly causes a financial burden. The system installation procedures in such a place are time-consuming and may disrupt the operation of the hospital to some extent. In particular, in hospital infrastructures that are not fully in tune with global technological developments in the healthcare sector, changes to the structure of the site and to the systems already in use are considered necessary. Only in this way will a modern tracking system be able to be implemented effectively and help medical staff.

Finally, finding a reliable such system is often difficult and the various technological organisations around the world bear a large share of the responsibility for this. Companies that manufacture and sell components necessary to build a tracking system in the field do not collaborate to build a single product but continue to focus on marketing their own products . [16]

Material	[dB]	Factor [-]
Dry Wall	1	0,8
Plywood	1 - 3	0,8 – 0,5
Glass	1 - 4	0,8 – 0,4
Painted Glass	10	0,1
Wood	2 - 9	0,6 – 0,1
Iron Mat	2 - 11	0,6 – 0,08
Roofing Tiles / Bricks	5 - 31	0,3 – 0,001
Concrete	12 - 43	0,06 – 0,00005
Ferro-Concrete	29 - 33	0,001 – 0,0005

Figure 7 . Signal attenuation by material and relative attenuation factor [15]

2.7 Healthcare using technology

The rapid technological development of recent years has greatly advanced the techniques and systems used in healthcare, offering new possibilities for the benefit of both doctors and patients.

2.7.1 Telemedicine and remote care

One of the rapidly emerging areas of healthcare is telemedicine, i.e. the use of modern information and telecommunication technologies to transfer medical data and provide healthcare at a distance. It refers to the diagnosis, treatment and prevention of a disease as well as scientific research and training of medical staff[17] . The term remote care is a subcategory of telemedicine and relates to communicating with the patient and monitoring his vital organs remotely in order to be independent of nurses and assistants. The doctor's communication with the patient in telemedicine can take place in real time or the information can be recorded at a specific time and sent later by email for example[17] . On the other hand, the type of information transmitted may be in the form of an image or even a video[17] , such as viewing the results of an MRI scan. Telemedicine includes all portable devices that incorporate sensors[18] and measure various vital signs of the individual such as blood pressure, body temperature and oxygen saturation in the blood. This data is then transferred to special remote servers via the internet[18] and stored in databases on a per-patient basis. Telemedicine is also used in emergency situations where the patient needs direct communication with the doctor[18] and through modern devices such as smartphones, a diagnosis can be made within minutes. Remote healthcare delivery will be implemented worldwide in the near future as it offers numerous advantages by evolving the quality of medical services. One of the most important that telemedicine offers is receiving high quality medical care in an immediate manner, thus providing a sense of comfort and safety comfort to the patient. It therefore becomes clear that barriers such as time and distance[18] , cease to exist, so that anyone can consult a specialist regardless of their location. It is also worth noting that the application of telemedicine significantly reduces the costs of health care facilities since the physical presence of patients in doctors' offices and hospitals is not required[18] . Finally,

doctors are in constant contact with the patient and monitor his/her health status at all times, which ensures more effective care and prevents any complications . [18]

2.7.2 Artificial intelligence and data analysis

In the last decade in particular, AI has been integrated into many areas of everyday human life and as a result it has started to be adopted in the healthcare sector as it offers new possibilities. AI in healthcare aims to create machine learning models that mimic human cognitive functions in order to enhance the delivery of patient care[19] . In particular, it is used in medical imaging and diagnosis as it helps in faster analysis of data such as an electrocardiogram[19] . It is also often applied in remote patient monitoring with the help of intelligent systems trained to analyse the data they receive in real time and transfer it to remote servers[19] . By rapidly analysing and processing data from medical research, AI can also be used in the creation of new pharmaceutical products and testing them on virtual patient models[19] . In addition, various machine learning models can be incorporated into software for rehabilitation devices and machines to evaluate patient progress based on signals received from these machines[19] . Finally, AI has the potential to reduce the time it takes to record and aggregate information in a hospital - such as all patients' histories and test results - thus increasing the efficiency of medical and nursing staff since they spend valuable time on the above[19] . However, the advantages and solutions offered by AI cannot negate the concerns and challenges it faces. Ethical issues regarding privacy, the replacement of doctors by machines in the near future and the ability of AI to make critical decisions[19] , cause reservations and second thoughts about its use. Another limitation that should not be overlooked is the high cost of installing AI systems and storing all the data .[19]

2.7.3 Prospects for the development of smart hospitals

The term smart hospital refers to hospitals that have incorporated the latest technological advances such as artificial intelligence, robotics and big data analysis to provide improved healthcare services[20] . The implementation of positioning systems for medical devices and nurses is one aspect of the smart hospital, which relies on short-range communication and data transmission technologies[20] . The tracking of both machinery and pharmaceuticals serves to manage equipment more efficiently and increase the quality of healthcare[20] . Another feature is the use of modern communication and information transfer techniques such as the 5G network or WiFi 6[20] . The same offer new possibilities to analyze and process large data packages generated daily, so the time spent on these issues can be allocated to more useful functions. A smart hospital uses techniques based on the Internet of Things (Internet of Things-IoT) to integrate sensor systems, specific software, web protocols and databases, which can, for example, reduce operating costs, shorten diagnosis time, ensure patient protection and optimise the use of medical consumables[20] . In addition, a smart hospital digitizes several operational processes using smartphones and sophisticated mobile devices, thus reducing paperwork and allowing medical staff to have instant access to any information at any time[20] . The integration also of artificial intelligence allows physicians to make more correct decisions regarding the diagnosis and prediction of a potential disease as analysis of a lot of medical data from trained models is achieved[20] . It should be noted that robotic systems are even being used in a smart hospital in order to improve the quality of care and patient experience. For example, robots have been built specifically for the field of surgery, which perform invasive procedures with higher precision than

the human hand, and robots intended for supportive patient care and automation of daily tasks in the hospital[20] . Finally, a smart hospital bases several of its services on telemedicine and augmented reality techniques. More specifically, through advanced technological devices, the patient can communicate directly with the doctor, who continuously monitors his/her health status with the help of wearable components. As far as augmented reality methods are concerned, there is virtual reality, augmented reality and mixed reality[20] . The first allows the user to connect to a virtual environment while using his or her senses, while the second provides information through digital media[20]

2.7.4 Security and data protection

With the evolution of the healthcare sector and its technological capabilities, it is understood that smart devices and systems will be increasingly used, which will transfer medical information to databases, thus digitizing all operational procedures[21] . In order to provide the highest quality care to the patient, hospitals and clinics store and transmit large volumes of personal patient data on a daily basis[21] . The data is related to each patient's personal information, their treatment history and test results, which may highlight their health status. They are divided into data that is stored directly in the memory of various mobile devices such as a smart watch with sensors and remains there, and data that is transferred from a device or machine to remote servers[22] . The first category is clearly more vulnerable because mobile devices do not have strong enough security while the second category is considered more secure since the transmission of information takes place over the internet and with special protocols[22] . Although the use of these data is aimed at more effective prevention and treatment, the privacy of patients and the security of the information must be constantly ensured as there are risks of leakage through cyber attacks or even human error[21] . It is quite important to establish legislative frameworks, if not already in place in all countries, in order to protect health data. In Europe, for example, the General Data Protection Regulation has been formulated to give individuals control over their personal data[22] . Also, in the United States, the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act-HIPAA has been enacted, which safeguards each patient's medical data such as their personal information, health status history, health care payment history, and the provision of care to third parties[22] . In addition to establishing regulations, medical organizations are required to use modern techniques to protect health data as new ways of intercepting information are constantly being created. Some of the techniques that have been developed so far are authentication, data encryption, data masking and access control[21] . The first technique allows access to a database only if the identity of the person wishing to log in is authenticated. The second technique converts all data into an encrypted form in order to make it impossible to read and therefore impossible to leak. Data masking relates to the modification and concealment of highly sensitive data - such as date of birth - so that it is not accessible to unauthorised intruders. Finally, the access control technique allows entry into an information system after identification but the capabilities within it are regulated and depend on the identity of[21] . In summary, the protection of medical data is of utmost importance for a modern healthcare system because it enhances the patient's trust in it.

3 Design and construction of the system

In this chapter, the problems for which the installation of a medical device positioning system within a hospital is considered necessary and the possibilities it offers to the end user are highlighted. It then focuses on the components and technologies used in its construction and explains how they interact with each other in order to make it clear how the system works. Finally, the stages of the implementation of this system are detailed in the order in which they were carried out to make it as clear and accessible as possible. These steps involve the programming of the electronic components used in specific software and the construction of the required electronic circuitry. In addition, the configuration of the backend - creation of the database and local server - and the frontend, which consists of the web page on which the location and operating status of the medical device is displayed, is explained.

3.1 Requirements and specifications

3.1.1 Issues resolved by the system

In order to define the requirements and specifications of the tracking system, contact was made with specialized medical personnel (doctors, nurses). Through this process, valuable information was collected on the needs and requirements that such a system should meet in the healthcare sector, as well as the features that would make it more functional and effective. To begin with, the real-time medical device and equipment tracking system helps medical and nursing staff to instantly locate the position of a device in the field. This feature is intended to reduce the time it takes to search for medical devices and equipment in any emergency situations, which can prove crucial in saving a patient's life. In addition, such a system serves to provide better quality healthcare for the patient and more efficient management of medical devices as it offers the possibility of notification in the event of a possible failure. This reduces the incidents of malfunctioning of valuable machinery and loss of important equipment. Finally, with the data provided by recording the movement history of each device within the hospital unit, unnecessary equipment purchases are prevented and the administrative staff can carry out supplies more accurately and in a more efficient manner.

3.1.2 System capabilities

This tracking system displays the position of the device of interest in two-dimensional plane and in real time in the form of a floor plan of the room and provides information on its operating status and notifies the end user in case of failure. The specific information along with the movement history and the activation history of the device is stored in a special database, making it possible for medical and nursing staff to view it at any time.

3.2 System architecture and technologies

The present medical device positioning system is based on Wi-Fi technology and consists of a Wi-Fi scanner, Wi-Fi access points and a central data processing system, which corresponds to a computer. This technology was chosen as the majority of hospitals have Wi-Fi networks, it offers the possibility of real-time monitoring and is also compatible with many systems and devices,

which reduces the cost of implementation since it does not require a specialized communication network.

3.2.1 Technologies and components

For the construction of this localization system four (4) Arduino MKR WiFi 1010 development boards, three (3) Raspberry Pi 5.1V power supplies, one (1) breadboard, two (2) slide-switch type switches, one (1) orange LED, one (1) green LED, one (1) 150Ω resistor, one 330Ω resistor and jumper cables were used. One of the four Arduino MKR Wi-Fi 1010 boards was programmed to act as a Wi-Fi scanner while the other three were programmed to act as Wi-Fi access points. Figure 8 shows the Arduino model and Figure 9 shows the power supply used. The software used to develop the code of each Arduino board is the Arduino IDE ([available here](#)). The IDLE (Python) programming environment ([available here](#)) was used to create the server on the local network and to configure the database, while the Visual Studio Code development environment ([available here](#)) was used to design the frontend of the user interface with the tracking system. Finally, the DB Browser for SQLite tool ([available here](#)) was used to store the data and categorize it.

Figure 8. Arduino MKR Wi-Fi 1010

Figure 9. Raspberry Pi 5.1V power supply

3.2.2 System architecture

The architecture of the real-time medical device tracking system is shown in Figure 10. Initially, each Arduino acting as a Wi-Fi access point creates its own Wi-Fi network, allowing other devices to connect to it. The Arduino acting as a Wi-Fi scanner, scans the surrounding area and detects information about available networks. The operation of the system in this paper relies on the Arduino's communicating via Wi-Fi as each of them incorporates a Wi-Fi module. In particular, the Wi-Fi scanner is tethered to the device whose location is desired to be monitored while each Wi-Fi access point is placed in a different room. As the medical device is moved, the Wi-Fi scanner detects the signals coming from each Wi-Fi access point and stores the strength of each signal in the form of a special indicator (Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI)). The Wi-Fi scanner then wirelessly transmits each indicator to the central processing unit. Special code determines the room in which the medical device is located according to the strength of each signal and projects its location on a floor plan of the room. The RSSI indicator always takes negative values (e.g., -30 dBm, -50 dBm, -80 dBm) and a larger (more positive) value means that the distance is shorter. This data is presented to the end user via a local network server to which he has free access.

Figure 10. Architecture of the implemented tracking system

3.3 Implementation and procedures

The following subsections discuss the implementation of the tracking system in the order in which each step was carried out.

3.3.1 Programming of Wi-Fi access points

With the help of the Arduino IDE software, the three (3) Arduinos were programmed to act as Wi-Fi access points and broadcast their own Wi-Fi network. A download of the WiFiNINA library was required, which allows communication with other devices via Wi-Fi technology. As shown in Code 1, Appendix A, the network name (SSID) and password of each access point is initially defined. In the setup() command, serial communication is initiated to monitor results and a 2-second delay is made for stabilization. The WiFi.beginAP() function creates the access point and in case of failure, an error message is displayed. If the creation is successful, the IP address is displayed with WiFi.localIP().

3.3.2 Electronic circuit construction

In order for the Arduino as a Wi-Fi scanner to provide information about the change of the operating state of the medical device in which it is integrated and also about a possible malfunction, it was important to develop a special electronic circuit. To create it, a breadboard, an orange LED, a green LED, two slide-switch type switches, a 150Ω resistor, a 330Ω resistor and jumper type cables were used. The representation of the circuit is shown in Figure 11 (the Arduino Uno was used for the simulation, but the function and pin layout used in the circuit are common to those of the Arduino MKR Wi-Fi 1010):

Figure 11. Illustration of the connection of the Arduino MKR to the breadboard (screenshot from Tinkercad software)

Initially the positive terminal of the breadboard was connected to the 5V power pin of the Arduino while the negative terminal of the breadboard was connected to the GND ground pin of the board. Next, the basic circuit of the two LEDs was designed, the schematic of which is shown in more detail in Figure 12. The green LED was connected to pin 3 of the Arduino and the orange LED was connected to pin 2 of the Arduino in order for the board to recognize when they are in HIGH (on) and when they are in LOW (off) states in order to transfer the data to the central processing unit. The Figure 13 shows the actual circuit.

Figure 12. Schematic of the circuit including the Arduino and the breadboard

Figure 13. Photo of the implemented circuit with the Arduino MKR Wi-Fi 1010 and the breadboard

3.3.3 Programming the Wi-Fi scanner

To program the Arduino that acts as a Wi-Fi scanner, the Wi-FiNINA library was also needed in order to be able to scan the available Wi-Fi networks and receive the signal coming from each access point. As shown in Code 2, Appendix A, the SSIDs and passwords for three different access points are defined at the beginning so that it can connect to them. Then with the `Serial.begin(9600)` command, the Arduino begins serial communication with the access points and is ready to receive data. `WiFi.status()` is used to detect if the Wi-Fi module is connected to the Arduino while the `getRSSI()` function is called to connect to each available Wi-Fi network and

obtain the strength of each signal (RSSI). If the connection fails, a value of 0 is returned, otherwise the RSSI value is returned. Finally, the `determineRoom()` function compares the RSSI values to determine which room has the best Wi-Fi signal. If the RSSI value is 0, it means the network is too far away or out of range. Depending on the stronger RSSI value, the Arduino identifies which room is closer to the access point.

To program the Arduino that acts as a Wi-Fi scanner, the `WiFinina` library was also needed in order to be able to detect the available Wi-Fi networks and receive the signal coming from each access point. In addition, it was mandatory to download the `SPI.h` library that supports the SPI (Serial Peripheral Interface) protocol to communicate the Arduino with the Wi-Fi module it carries and `Arduino.h`, which includes some basic commands. As shown in Code 2, Appendix A, the SSIDs and passwords for three different access points are defined at the beginning so that the Wi-Fi scanner can connect to them. In the `setup()` function, serial communication with the three access points is initiated and the LED pins are defined as inputs with the `pinMode()` function. Then, `scanNetworks()` is used to scan all available networks. If one of the SSIDs corresponds to a predefined access point, the signal strength (RSSI) is stored. The `determineRoom()` function compares the RSSI values received by the Arduino and decides which room the device is in. The result is recorded if the position changes from the previous measurement. The `logRoomChange()` function transfers the name of the room via the serial port to communicate with a Python script.

3.3.4 Creating a database

The next step was to create a code in Python programming language using IDLE software to read the data extracted by the Wi-Fi scanner and store it in a database. Necessary libraries for this code were `serial` (`PySerial`) which provides functions for serial communication between the computer and external devices, the `sqlite3` library which allows the creation and management of a SQLite database and `datetime` which is used to record the timestamp of the data. Observing Code 3, Appendix A, the command `serial.Serial('COM12', 9600)` opens a serial connection to the COM12 port corresponding to the Arduino in the Wi-Fi scanner role. Then, the functions `location_conn = sqlite3.connect('location_history.db')` and `led_conn = sqlite3.connect('device_led_history.db')` create a database to store the locations and status of the LEDs respectively. The `CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS LocationHistory` and `CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS DeviceLedHistory` commands create tables for the two databases and changes to them are stored via `location_conn.commit()` and `led_conn.commit()` respectively. The `while True` loop continuously reads data from the serial port with `ser.readline()` if available (`ser.in_waiting > 0`). Finally, the `if "Location:"` in line checks if the message received from the Arduino contains information. If there is location information, it registers it in the `LocationHistory` table accompanied by its timestamp, while if the message is about a change in the state of an LED, it is recorded in the `DeviceLEDHistory` table with a timestamp.

3.3.5 Create server

To present the information in real time it was necessary to set up a server. Important libraries for this purpose are `serial`, `sqlite3`, `datetime`, `threading` which allows managing parallel processes to read data without affecting the server, and `flask` and `flask_socketio`, which create the server and support real-time updates via WebSockets. WebSockets are a special communication protocol

between user and server that allows data to be sent in both directions without repeated requests. As shown in Code 4, Appendix A, after the libraries are imported, a connection is established to the COM12 serial port and 9600 baud speed, corresponding to the Arduino (Wi-Fi scanner), with the command `serial.Serial('COM12', 9600)`. With `app = Flask(__name__)` a Flask object is created representing the web application that the user will access. WebSockets support is then added with the command `socketio = SocketIO(app)`. The `sqlite3.connect()` function establishes a connection to the two databases created previously (`location_history.db`, `device_led_history.db`). As for the transfer of information to the server, `@socketio.on('connect')` manages the connection of a client (web browser) to the server, `socketio.emit('status_update', {...})` updates in real time about changes in location and status of LEDs. Finally, the `threading.Thread(target= read_serial, daemon= True).start()` function enables reading data from COM12 port on request from the server and `socketio.run(app, host='0.0.0.0', port=5000)` activates it and makes it available for the end user.

3.3.6 Creation of the website

The last step in order to complete the implementation process of the medical device tracking system was clearly the design of a web page to allow the user to monitor the position of the Wi-Fi scanner (Arduino) and the status of its LEDs in real time. Visual Studio Code was used as the development environment as it supports several programming languages (HTML, CSS, JavaScript, Python etc.) and was considered the most ideal for combining the backend and frontend of the tracking system. Code 5 - presented in Appendix A - uses the Socket.IO library, which allows communication between clients and web servers in both directions for real-time web applications. The style section of the code consists of CSS commands that shape the appearance of the web page to the user. Initially, the `.floor-plan` element is created which is the image of room locations in floor plan format. The `.dot` class defines the format of a dot which will symbolize the location of the medical device in the room and the `.repair-message` displays the message "Device needs repair" on the screen when the orange LED is activated. The HTML section follows and after defining the HTML elements in `<body>`, the Socket.IO library is loaded with the command `<script src="https://cdn.socket.io/...">` while in the Javascript code a WebSocket connection to the server is made via the `const socket = io();` command. Then the coordinates of the dot's location in each room are specified and the function `startOrangeBlinking()` is created which is associated with "blinking" the dot to orange and displaying the repair message. At this point in the code there is no corresponding function for the green LED as it is desired to give priority to orange since it is associated with a device failure. The existence of this priority is specified in the `if (led_state)` loop. Finally, the function `stopBlinking()` is responsible for resetting the color of the dot to its original state when the orange LED ceases to be active.

4 System test and results

This chapter presents the experimental implementation of the medical device tracking system and gives details about the test environment, the locations where the different components of the system were placed and all the measurement conditions. Photographs of the actual circuit constructed in its various operating states are also shown. As for the measurements taken during the experimental procedure, their analysis is carried out, focusing on a general comparison through the mean values and standard deviations in order to obtain a first estimation of the system performance. Still, along with the reference to the response time of the two LEDs and the response time of the location, snapshots from the web app are provided, which illustrate the room change as well as the transition between different operating states. Finally, a statistical analysis of the results is performed, which provides more accuracy and reliability in data comparison. In particular, the results and conclusions of the T-Test, ANOVA test and confidence interval are presented.

4.1 Test operation of the system

The test of the detection system was carried out inside a house and in rooms with brick walls. Initially, a Wi-Fi access point connected to the power supply via a Raspberry Pi 5.1V power supply was placed in each of the rooms. The choice of each outlet was made with the aim of keeping the three access points as far apart as possible. For example, it was not desirable to place two Arduinos on the same wall socket, as it was necessary to limit any possibility of the two signals overlapping, potentially affecting the positioning calculation in the room. The Arduino in the role of a Wi-Fi scanner was connected to a laptop via a special USB Type A-Micro USB cable in order to be on a continuous power supply. The procedure of the experiment was to move the Wi-Fi scanner (along with the laptop) between three rooms and turn on/off the two LEDs alternately or simultaneously in order to determine the functionality of the system. During testing, two key system response times were recorded. The first was the time required to move the dot in the web app from one room to another after the device changed location in the room. The second was the time it took for the color of the dot in the web app to change once one of the LEDs was activated. It is important to note that in testing the response time of the LEDs in each room, the Wi-Fi scanner was not moving and was one meter away from the corresponding access point each time so that the measurements had the same parameters. In the first scenario of the experiment, the 3 Wi-Fi access points were placed in adjacent rooms. In the first phase and using a timer, the location response time in each room was measured, starting the timer at the moment the Wi-Fi scanner passed the door of the respective room. Next, the response time of the LEDs in each room was calculated, both for turning them on and off, with the Wi-Fi scanner in a fixed position and not moving. In the second phase the same measurements were performed but with the room doors closed to assess signal interference. In the second scenario, exactly the same tests were performed as in the first one except that the Wi-Fi access points were placed in 3 non-adjacent rooms to evaluate whether the greater distance between rooms affects the signal attenuation and, consequently, the performance of the tracking system. The following images (Figure 14, Figure 15, Figure 16) show the operation of the circuit during the experimental tests with the green LED on, the orange LED on and both LEDs on simultaneously.

Figure 14. Photo of the Wi-Fi scanner's electrical circuit with the green LED turned on

Figure 15. Photo of the Wi-Fi scanner's electrical circuit with the orange LED turned on

Figure 16. Photo of the Wi-Fi scanner's electrical circuit with both LEDs turned on

4.2 Results

In each scenario and in each test phase, the measurements were repeated 10 times to ensure the reliability and accuracy of the results, taking into account any variations that may be due to factors such as signal attenuation from obstacles and system operating conditions. In this way, the average response time of each category was calculated in order to have a more complete picture of the system behaviour.

4.2.1 LED response time

LED response time is defined as the time it takes for the colour of the dot representing the medical device to change in the web app. While it is out of order, the dot is represented in red. In case the green LED, which symbolizes that the device is on, is activated, the dot turns green. If the orange LED is activated, signifying that the medical device has developed a technical fault and requires repair, the colour of the dot shall turn orange and an appropriate message shall be displayed on the screen. It is important to mention that the orange LED has priority over the green LED because a potential malfunction must be corrected immediately. This means that when both LEDs are on, the software will ignore the green one. The change in the color of the dot depending on the activation of the LEDs is shown in Figure 17, Figure 18 and Figure 19.

Figure 17. View the location of the medical device via web app when it is out of service in room 3

Figure 18. View the location of the medical device via web app when it is in use in room 3

Figure 19. View the location of the medical device via web app when it is in room 3 and needs repair

In the first test scenario (the Wi-Fi access points were located in adjacent rooms), the response time of activation and deactivation of each LED in the 3 adjacent rooms was measured and the average value with the room doors open and closed was calculated. Then, the same measurements were performed except that the three Wi-Fi access points were placed in non-adjacent rooms (second test scenario) and the average value was again calculated with both room doors open and closed. The purpose of this was to examine the effect of distance on the Wi-Fi signal and possible attenuation by obstacles such as doors. The average value of the on and off time of each LED for all 3 rooms in total in each possible condition is shown in the Table 1.

Table 1. Average on and off time of each LED under different conditions

LED	Phase	Condition	Average activation time (sec)	Average deactivation time (sec)
orange	neighbouring rooms	open doors	2,58	2,52
orange	neighbouring rooms	closed doors	2,85	2,94
green	neighbouring rooms	open doors	3,14	2,55
green	neighbouring rooms	closed doors	3,45	3,42
orange	non-adjacent rooms	open doors	2,97	3,36
orange	non-adjacent rooms	closed doors	3,48	3,46
green	non-adjacent rooms	open doors	3,33	2,63
green	non-adjacent rooms	closed doors	3,34	3,98

In Table 2, the time difference of the average on and off time of each LED between phase A-B for the 2 test scenarios is shown. By observing the values, it can be seen that the closed room doors had minimal effect on the LED response time as these small time differences are considered almost negligible. It can be seen that also in the case in which the Wi-Fi access points were placed in non-adjacent rooms, the closed doors of the rooms had almost no effect on the LED response

time. Also, comparing the average response times of the two LEDs for the two scenarios, it is clear that neither the increase in distance had a significant effect but instead the time difference is minimal and in a medical device tracking system can be ignored. These values demonstrate that the operation of the two LEDs remains stable regardless of the conditions of the localization system and their temporal response is almost identical.

Table 2. Difference in average on and off time between phase A and B of each LED

LED	Phase	Difference in average activation time (Phase A - Phase B) (sec)	Difference in average switch-off time (Phase A - Phase B) (sec)
orange	neighbouring rooms	0,27	0,42
green	neighbouring rooms	0,31	0,87
orange	non-adjacent rooms	0,51	0,1
green	non-adjacent rooms	0,01	1,35

Table 3 , shows the difference of the average on - off time of each LED in each possible condition of the two test scenarios. The same was calculated to find out whether either of the two LEDs has better time performance compared to the other. It is evident that this time difference is less than one second, which indicates that the two LEDs perform with the same stability.

Table 3. Difference in average on/off time of each LED

LED	Phase	Condition	Difference of average on/off time (sec)
orange	neighbouring rooms	open doors	0,06
orange	neighbouring rooms	closed doors	0,09
green	neighbouring rooms	open doors	0,59
green	neighbouring rooms	closed doors	0,03
orange	non-adjacent rooms	open doors	0,39
orange	non-adjacent rooms	closed doors	0,02
green	non-adjacent rooms	open doors	0,7
green	non-adjacent rooms	closed doors	0,64

Another quantity that can represent the reliability of the system and the stability of the values obtained is the standard deviation. As shown in Table 4 and Table 5 , the average standard deviation for each LED in each different test condition is quite small for a localization system based on Wi- Fi technology. It should be noted that the standard deviation was calculated in total for the on and off of each LED. These values also indicate that the system has small variations in its performance, which confirms that it is responding as expected. In addition, the recording of the LED state change was accurately recorded in the database, ensuring that the LEDs were correctly captured. Figure 18 shows a snapshot of the database.

Table 4. Average standard deviation of the response time of the two LEDs under different conditions (1st test scenario - ground rooms)

LED	Condition	Room 1 (s) (sec)	Room 2 (s) (sec)	Room 3 (s) (sec)	Mean standard deviation ($\bar{\sigma}$)
orange	open doors	1,26	0,96	1,28	1,17
orange	closed doors	1,3	1,15	1,09	1,19
green	open doors	1,38	0,98	0,99	1,12
green	closed doors	1,24	0,8	1,28	1,1

Table 5. Average standard deviation of the response time of the two LEDs in different conditions (2nd test scenario - no adjacent rooms)

Condition	LED	Room 1 (s) (sec)	Room 2 (s) (sec)	Room 3 (s) (sec)	Mean standard deviation ($\bar{\sigma}$)
Open doors	orange	1,22	1,07	1,71	1,33
Closed doors	orange	1,57	1,23	1,49	1,43
Open doors	green	1,75	1,67	1,73	1,71
Closed doors	green	1,36	1,39	1,73	1,49

Green	ON	2025-01-19 13:59:35
Orange	ON	2025-01-19 14:00:18
Orange	OFF	2025-01-19 14:00:54
Green	OFF	2025-01-19 14:01:36

Figure 20. Recorded times and states of the LEDs in the database

4.2.2 Site response time

The location response time of the tracking system refers to the time it takes from the moment the medical device with the Wi-Fi scanner changes rooms in the room to the moment the web app displays this change. The medical device is symbolized by a dot, which moves from room to room in an image showing the floor plan of three hospital beds. The system shows the location of the device in each room as shown in Figure 21, Figure 22, and Figure 23.

Figure 21. View of the medical device in room 1 in working mode (screenshot from the web app)

Figure 22. View of the medical device in room 2 in working mode (screenshot from the web app)

Figure 23. View of the medical device in room 3 in working mode (screenshot from the web app)

As for the position update response time measured during the system test, 10 recordings were made in each room and for each possible scenario. This was done in order to determine whether the location response time depends on the particular room that the Wi-Fi scanner enters, but also on factors such as the conditions (open or closed doors) and the distance between rooms (adjacent or non-adjacent). The Table 6 shows the average location response time in each room and for each possible condition. The standard deviation for this response time was then calculated to determine the stability of the localization system and any potential problem with it in case it differs significantly from the mean value. The average standard deviation then calculated for each room and each possible condition is shown in

Table 7.

Table 6. Average site response time for each room in different conditions

Scenario/Phase	Room 1 (sec)	Room 2 (sec)	Room 3 (sec)	Overall average (sec)
Neighbours (open doors)	5,62	5,28	6,93	5,94
Neighbours (closed doors)	4,5	2,79	8,5	5,26
Non-adjacent (open doors)	4,64	3,96	4,58	4,4
Non-adjacent (closed doors)	6,49	3,41	6,73	5,54

Table 7. Average standard deviation of site response time under different conditions

Scenario/Phase	Room 1 (s) (sec)	Room 2 (s) (sec)	Room 3 (s) (sec)	Mean standard deviation ($\bar{\sigma}$) (sec)
Neighbours (open doors)	2,04	2,3	0,81	1,72
Neighbours (closed doors)	2,47	2,54	0,63	1,88
Non-adjacent (open doors)	0,56	1,12	2,46	1,38
Non-adjacent (closed doors)	2,27	1,89	2,29	2,15

Taking into account the data on the average response time of the position and the standard deviation of its measurements, it can be concluded that the system is reliable for locating a medical device in space. The values of the average location response time for each possible test scenario are almost identical and are within a small margin of each other. This indicates that both the distance between the rooms in which the Wi-Fi scanners were placed and the closed doors have no noticeable effect on the Wi-Fi signal. The average location response time per room, estimated at 5.28 seconds, regardless of experimental conditions, is considered normal for a Wi-Fi based tracking system. This finding is reasonable, given that even modern mobile phones take a few seconds to connect to an Internet network. Finally, the standard deviation calculated for the location response times measured in each different scenario reveals that the measured values show small deviations around the mean. This suggests that this particular localization system is effective as the response time remains constant under different conditions. It is worth noting that the effectiveness of the system is also shown by the accuracy with which the changes in the location of the medical device are recorded in the database, allowing reliable tracking of the location history. Figure 24 is a snapshot of the database.

465	Room 3	2025-01-22 15:16:07
466	Room 2	2025-01-22 15:17:21
467	Room 1	2025-01-22 15:18:00
468	Room 3	2025-01-22 15:18:36

Figure 24. Recorded times and corresponding rooms in the database

4.3 Statistical analysis of results

This section deals with the statistical analysis of the data collected during the experimental tests, in order to draw more informed and safer conclusions about the performance of the system. In particular, T-Test, analysis of variance (ANOVA) and confidence intervals calculation are applied to identify possible differences in LED and site response times under different test conditions. The results of the above analyses provide a quantitative assessment of the stability and reliability of the system implemented in this work.

4.3.1 T-Test

First, the T-Test was performed on the measurements taken during the experimental tests of the tracking system. This is a statistical test that compares the mean values of two data sets to test whether the difference between them is statistically significant or due to random variation. The T-Test outputs a value per pair of data, which is called the p-value. If $p\text{-value} < 0.05$ then there is a statistically significant difference, if $p\text{-value} > 0.05$ then there is no statistically significant difference and if $p\text{-value} = 0.05$ then it is considered a borderline case. The Microsoft Excel equation $T.TEST(\text{array1}, \text{array2}, \text{tails}, \text{type})$ was used to calculate each value where array1 and array2 are the arrays of the desired data pair while tails (values=1,2) and type (values=1,2,3) are the parameters that determine how the data is compared. T-Test in particular was applied to compare the response time of each LED and the position response time under different conditions and scenarios. It should be noted that this comparison was done per room pairs at a time. Table 8 shows the p-value values calculated for the LED response time

Table 8. p-value extracted from the T-Test for the response time of each LED per room pairs

LED	Phase	Condition	p-value (Room 1 vs 2)	p-value (Room 2 vs 3)	p-value (Room 3 vs 1)
orange	neighbouring rooms	open doors	0,08	0,49	0,06
green	neighbouring rooms	open doors	0,56	0,02	0,02
orange	neighbouring rooms	closed doors	0,21	0,5	0,05
green	neighbouring rooms	closed doors	0,79	0,99	0,82
orange	non-adjacent rooms	open doors	0,42	0,18	0,58
green	non-adjacent rooms	open doors	0,17	0,73	0,32
orange	non-adjacent rooms	closed doors	0,45	0,15	0,43
green	non-adjacent rooms	closed doors	0,05	0,72	0,19

As shown in the table above, of the 24 p-value values, only 4 values (0.02-0.02-0.05-0.05) show statistically significant differences, while the remaining 20 are greater than 0.05. Since the vast majority of the p-values (20/24) are greater than 0.05, the system shows generally stable performance in LED response time, as no statistically significant differences are observed between comparisons. The 4 lower p-value values (≤ 0.05) may be due to random measurement errors or factors not fully accounted for, but are not sufficient to negate the overall stability of the system. Therefore, based on the data, the system is reliable and operates in a consistent manner as far as the performance of the two LEDs is concerned.

The T-Test was then applied to the data concerning the location response time, i.e. the time between the moment when the actual location of the medical device changes and the moment when the system records and displays its new location in space. The Table 9 shows the p-value values for the location response time.

Table 9. p-values extracted from the T-Test for location response time by room pairs

Phase	Condition	p-value (Room 1 vs 2)	p-value (Room 2 vs 3)	p-value (Room 3 vs 1)
neighbouring rooms	open doors	0,73	0,06	0,08
neighbouring rooms	closed doors	0,14	$3,94 \times 10^{-5}$	$5,52 \times 10^{-4}$
non-adjacent rooms	open doors	0,11	0,48	0,94
non-adjacent rooms	closed doors	$4,17 \times 10^{-3}$	$2,47 \times 10^{-3}$	0,81

Considering the 12 p-value values of the above table, in most scenarios they are greater than 0.05 proving that there is no statistically significant difference in response time between rooms. This means that the system performs with relative stability in most cases. However, there are 4 values significantly less than 0.05 (3.94×10^{-5} , 5.52×10^{-4} , 4.17×10^{-3} and 2.47×10^{-3}), indicating that in this particular case the system may have a larger variation in response time between the respective rooms. In particular, when the rooms are adjacent and the doors are closed, room 3 is statistically significantly different from both room 2 and room 1. Also, when the rooms are not adjacent and the doors are closed, there is a significant difference between Room 1 and Room 2, as well as between Room 2 and Room 3. These results show that barriers ultimately affect the performance of the system. In the previous section, the mean and standard deviation calculated gave a first estimate that they do not cause signal attenuation and therefore do not affect the location response speed. However, the use of the T-Test revealed that there is a statistically significant effect of obstacles, in which case it is the room doors. This means that the difference may be small but systematic, which cannot be seen simply by comparing means and standard deviations.

4.3.2 Analysis of Variance - ANOVA Test

ANOVA (Analysis Of Variance) is a statistical method used to compare more than two groups of data at the same time and to see if there is a statistically significant difference between the means of these groups. As for the values it outputs - in the present tracking system - if the p-value is less

than 0.05, it means that there is at least one room with a different average response time from the others, while if the p-value is greater than 0.05, there is no statistically significant difference, and therefore the response times in the 3 rooms can be considered similar. To calculate the p-value, the Microsoft Excel analysis tool package was used to calculate the p-value, in which the ANOVA: Single Factor method was applied. Specifically, through the Data > Data Analysis > ANOVA: Single Factor option, the data range was defined and a significance level of $\alpha=0.05$ was set. From the results, the p-value was extracted for each group of data. In this particular case, a comparison of the LED response time and location response time values was performed for all 3 rooms simultaneously. Table 10 shows the p-value values calculated for the response time of each LED.

Table 10. ANOVA test p-values for the response time of each LED and for the 3 rooms in total

LED	Phase	Condition	p-value
orange	neighbouring rooms	open doors	0,07
green	neighbouring rooms	open doors	0,02
orange	neighbouring rooms	closed doors	0,13
green	neighbouring rooms	closed doors	0,95
orange	non-adjacent rooms	open doors	0,39
green	non-adjacent rooms	open doors	0,37
orange	non-adjacent rooms	closed doors	0,31
green	non-adjacent rooms	closed doors	0,18

Looking at the above table of p-value values for the response time of each LED, in almost all cases, the p-value is greater than 0.05, meaning that there are no statistically significant differences in response time between rooms. The only exception is the green LED in adjacent rooms with open doors ($p = 0.02$), where there is a statistically significant difference. Clearly, this alone is not sufficient to conclude that the green LED has a different performance compared to the orange LED. The observed difference may be due to random measurement errors or other uncontrollable factors. Furthermore, with a larger number of measurements, the result could be different, possibly leading to a non-statistically significant difference. Therefore, according to the ANOVA test, the system has a relatively stable behavior and the LED response times are similar between the 3 rooms.

In the next step, the same test was performed to compare the location response time to see if this time differs between the 3 rooms. The Table 11 shows the p-value values calculated.

Table 11. ANOVA test p-values for location response time for all 3 rooms in total

Phase	Condition	p-value
neighbouring rooms	open doors	0,12
neighbouring rooms	closed doors	$4,9 \times 10^{-6}$
non-adjacent rooms	open doors	0,57
non-adjacent rooms	closed doors	0,02

According to Table 11, the p-values that are greater than 0.05 are those corresponding to the 2 cases where the room doors are open. On the other hand, the p-values that are less than 0.05 are those corresponding to the cases where the doors of the rooms are closed. This suggests that

barriers have a significant effect on the location response time, as both adjacent and non-adjacent rooms show statistically significant differences with the doors closed. In contrast, location/position response time is similar in all rooms regardless of their distance and when the doors are open.

4.3.3 Confidence Interval - Confidence Interval

In the third and final step of the statistical analysis of the system results, the confidence interval was applied, which is a method that complements the results of the T-Test and ANOVA. Specifically, it is a range of values that contains the true mean of a population with a certain probability (usually 95%). That is, it indicates what range the true mean is expected to be in, based on the data collected from a sample, rather than simply testing whether there is a statistically significant difference. In this case, it helps to evaluate the stability of the tracking system and whether the measurements taken are affected by external factors such as obstacles (doors) and the distance between rooms. The CONFIDENCE.T(alpha, standard deviation, size) function was used to calculate the confidence interval, where alpha is the significance level and was set to 0.05 as a 95% probability selection was made, standard deviation is the standard deviation of the data in question and size is the size of the data, i.e. the number of data. The lower bound is equal to the smallest value that the true average response time can take, while the upper bound is equal to the largest value that the true average response time can take. As far as his results are concerned, if the confidence intervals calculated overlap each other, then there are no significant differences for the response times between rooms.

First, confidence intervals were calculated for the response time of each LED in all rooms and each possible condition to determine whether obstacles (room doors) and the distance between rooms played a decisive role in the measurements taken during the experimental operation of the tracking system. TheTable 12 shows the calculated confidence intervals for the orange LED and theTable 13 for the green LED

Table 12. Confidence intervals for the response time of the orange LED in each room

Phase	Condition	Room	Lower limit (sec)	Upper limit (sec)
neighbouring rooms	open doors	1	2,36	3,82
neighbouring rooms	open doors	2	2,04	2,79
neighbouring rooms	open doors	3	1,38	2,92
neighbouring rooms	closed doors	1	2,73	3,96
neighbouring rooms	closed doors	2	2,13	3,50
neighbouring rooms	closed doors	3	1,96	3,12
non-adjacent rooms	open doors	1	2,45	3,84
non-adjacent rooms	open doors	2	2,94	4,00
non-adjacent rooms	open doors	3	2,13	3,65
non-adjacent rooms	closed doors	1	2,85	4,09
non-adjacent rooms	closed doors	2	3,11	4,46
non-adjacent rooms	closed doors	3	2,50	3,80

Table 13. Confidence intervals for the green LED response time in each room

Phase	Condition	Room	Lower limit (sec)	Upper limit (sec)
-------	-----------	------	-------------------	-------------------

neighbouring rooms	open doors	1	2,45	4,31
neighbouring rooms	open doors	2	2,51	3,67
neighbouring rooms	open doors	3	1,43	2,72
neighbouring rooms	closed doors	1	2,83	4,17
neighbouring rooms	closed doors	2	2,99	3,82
neighbouring rooms	closed doors	3	2,73	4,07
non-adjacent rooms	open doors	1	1,39	3,48
non-adjacent rooms	open doors	2	2,31	4,43
non-adjacent rooms	open doors	3	1,99	4,27
non-adjacent rooms	closed doors	1	3,57	4,77
non-adjacent rooms	closed doors	2	2,59	4,03
non-adjacent rooms	closed doors	3	2,56	4,43

As mentioned earlier, to determine if there is a significant difference in LED response time between rooms, it is necessary to calculate whether the confidence intervals of the 3 rooms overlap. To make the overlap easier to understand, a simple example is given. For the orange LED and for the adjacent rooms with the doors open, the confidence interval of room 1 is [2.36 - 3.82] and that of room 2 is [2.04 - 2.79]. It is observed that the two intervals overlap because their common part is [2.36 - 2.79]. This overlap shows that the two sets of data do not show a significant difference. As for the other cases of the orange LED, the confidence interval values show significant overlap between the rooms in each scenario and condition. This suggests that there is no statistically significant difference between rooms, i.e. the response of the orange LED is stable regardless of location and conditions. Regarding the green LED, again in most cases the confidence intervals overlap meaning that the response time of the green LED is also stable between rooms. Therefore, the calculation of the confidence intervals confirms that the response time of the two LEDs is consistent and is not affected by the presence in any particular room out of the 3.

Next, confidence intervals were calculated for the site response time in each room. The purpose of this was to determine whether this time was stable in all rooms and under all possible conditions. The following is the Table 14 with the confidence intervals for the location/site response time.

Table 14. Confidence intervals for site response time in each room

Phase	Condition	Room	Lower limit (sec)	Upper limit (sec)
neighbouring rooms	open doors	1	4,15	7,08
neighbouring rooms	open doors	2	3,63	6,93
neighbouring rooms	open doors	3	6,35	7,51
neighbouring rooms	closed doors	1	2,73	6,28
neighbouring rooms	closed doors	2	0,97	4,61
neighbouring rooms	closed doors	3	8,04	8,96
non-adjacent rooms	open doors	1	4,24	5,05
non-adjacent rooms	open doors	2	3,16	4,77
non-adjacent rooms	open doors	3	2,82	6,35
non-adjacent rooms	closed doors	1	4,86	8,11

non-adjacent rooms	closed doors	2	2,05	4,76
non-adjacent rooms	closed doors	3	5,09	8,37

Based on the above table, some conclusions can be drawn about the response time of the site. In the cases with the doors open, the confidence intervals overlap, which proves that the response times do not differ significantly between rooms. Under closed door conditions, the intervals of room 3 do not overlap with the intervals of the other two rooms, indicating possible differences in response times due to the obstacles. These results, confirm the T-Test and ANOVA Test, which also showed that room doors significantly affect the response time of the system location.

5 Conclusions and future improvements

The measurement results of this work have revealed significant findings on the performance and reliability of the real-time medical device tracking system. This chapter presents the main conclusions about the performance and reliability of the system after a general analysis of the measurements and specific statistical tests. Future improvements that can be applied to the localization system of this thesis and prospects for further development are also presented in order to increase its accuracy, its capabilities and to more easily deal with possible challenges.

5.1 Evaluation of system functionality

The analysis of the measurements taken, which was carried out in two stages, led to a number of conclusions. In the first stage, a comparison of the mean values and standard deviations of the LED response time and the site response time was carried out. The results showed that these two times remain stable and are not significantly affected by factors such as increasing distance and obstacles (doors). In the second stage, a statistical analysis of the measurements between the 3 rooms was performed in order to provide a more detailed and objective examination of the values and to make the results more reliable. 3 statistical tests applied (T-Test, ANOVA test and confidence interval) indicated that the response time of the two LEDs did not show statistically significant differences and remained stable in all rooms regardless of conditions and scenarios. As for the location response time, it was shown to have small variations between the three rooms and is quite reliable. On the other hand, however, all three statistical tests performed showed that the obstacles (doors) interfering with the Wi-Fi signal path have a statistically significant effect on the location response time. Although the simple comparison of the means and standard deviations led to the conclusion that the location response time remains constant under different conditions, the statistical analysis revealed that the obstacles affect its performance. Since statistical tests offer greater reliability and substantiation, their conclusions are adopted as more valid. Despite the detectable effect of the obstacles, the resulting differences are not so significant as to affect the functionality of the system at this scale. However, it is worth bearing in mind that in larger spaces or environments with increased obstacles, the accuracy of a Wi-Fi tracking system may present challenges.

In general terms, the experimental test carried out has shown that this tracking system reliably meets its objectives. These are to track the location of a medical device and its real-time operating status. After the measurements taken and their extraction, it is confirmed that the system can be implemented indoors without any problem and can continuously transmit information. For real-time applications it is quite practical and easy to use since its installation is done within a few minutes and can be used by anyone with very general knowledge in this field. Some examples of places where it can be applied beyond hospitals are warehouses, airports, smart homes and even livestock units. Finally, no major challenges were encountered during the tests that made the system difficult to operate. However, it is perfectly logical that some issues may arise if it is implemented in a much larger area and for monitoring more devices. The limitations can certainly be resolved as they are naturally created by the increase in requirements.

5.2 Future extensions

With the completion of the experimental tests and the overall evaluation of the tracking system, some prospects for further upgrades are emerging, which will enhance its performance and capabilities. One of the most important improvements that can be made is to increase the number of Wi-Fi access points, so that they can even be present in the corridors connecting the rooms. This will avoid errors in location estimation, where the app may show the device in a particular room when it is actually in the hallway. This can happen due to the RSSI values received by the Wi-Fi scanner. This will ensure a more accurate location of the device especially in rooms with larger dimensions and more rooms. In order for the system to be able to track the location of multiple devices simultaneously, a new Wi-Fi scanner should be integrated each additional medical device. In case the tracking of the exact coordinates of the medical device is desired, the triangulation method, which is based on geometry, can be used. In particular, it calculates the position of an object using its distances from at least three known points, which are the Wi-Fi access points. Another extension of the system is the conversion to wireless. To do this, the Wi-Fi scanner must be connected to a long-life battery so that it does not need to be constantly replaced. A reliable solution is Li-ion (lithium) and Li-Po (lithium-polymer) batteries, which are rechargeable and have a long lifespan. In terms of ease of use, the electronic circuitry on the breadboard could be transferred to a PCB to make it smaller in size and more flexible. As for its protection, it is suggested to add a transparent plastic enclosure that can be opened and closed to activate the LED switches. Lastly, in applications of the tracking system in environments and places where large packets of information are collected, it would be useful and beneficial to develop additional data protection mechanisms. For example, providing each person with access to the system with a unique code is a solution that largely guarantees the controlled transfer and use of their data.

Annex A

Code 1 - Programming access points in Arduino IDE

```
#include< WiFiNINA.h>

const char* ssid = "Arduino_AP1"; // Replace with your desired SSID
const char* password = "123456789"; // Replace with your desired
password

void setup() {
  Serial.begin(9600);

  // Wait for a short duration to allow the board to stabilize
  delay(2000); // Delay for 2 seconds

  // Start the Access Point
  if (WiFi.beginAP(ssid, password) != WL_AP_LISTENING) {
    Serial.println("Failed to create Access Point");;
    while (true); // Stop if AP creation fails
  }

  Serial.println("Access Point started");;
  Serial.print("IP Address: ");
  Serial.println(WiFi.localIP());;
}

void loop() {
  // No action needed in the loop for now
}
```

Code 2 - Programming the Wi-Fi scanner in Arduino IDE

```
#include <WiFiNINA.h>
#include <SPI.h>
#include <Arduino.h>

// Access point details
const char* ssid1 = "Arduino_AP1"; // Access Point 1 SSID
const char* ssid2 = "Arduino_AP2"; // Access Point 2 SSID
const char* ssid3 = "Arduino_AP3"; // Access Point 3 SSID

// Variables to hold RSSI values
long rssi1, rssi2, rssi3;
String lastRoom = ""; // To store the last detected room

// Green LED slide switch pin
const int greenLEDPin = 3; // Slide switch pin for green LED
const int orangeLEDPin = 2; // Slide switch pin for orange LED
```

```

// Variables to track the state of the green and orange LED switches
int currentGreenState = LOW; // Current state of the green LED switch
int previousGreenState = LOW; // Previous state of the green LED switch

int currentOrangeState = LOW; // Current state of the orange LED switch
int previousOrangeState = LOW; // Previous state of the orange LED
switch

void setup() {
  Serial.begin(9600);
  while (!Serial) { ; ; } // Wait for serial port to connect
  Serial.println("WiFi Scanner Initialized");

  // Set the green and orange LED's slide switch pins as inputs
  pinMode(greenLEDPin, INPUT);;
  pinMode(orangeLEDPin, INPUT);;
}

void loop() {
  // Monitor orange LED switch state
  currentOrangeState = digitalRead(orangeLEDPin);

  if (currentOrangeState != previousOrangeState) {
    if (currentOrangeState == HIGH) {
      Serial.println("Device needs repair"); // Orange LED is
ON
    } else {
      Serial.println("Orange LED turned OFF"); // Orange LED is
OFF
    }
    previousOrangeState = currentOrangeState;
  }

  // Monitor green LED switch state, only consider if orange is OFF
  currentGreenState = digitalRead(greenLEDPin);
  if (currentOrangeState == LOW) { // Green LED is only checked when
orange is OFF
    if (currentGreenState != previousGreenState) {
      if (currentGreenState == HIGH) {
        Serial.println("Device turned ON"); // Green LED is
ON
      } else {
        Serial.println("Device turned OFF"); // Green LED is
OFF
      }
      previousGreenState = currentGreenState;
    }
  }

  // Scan WiFi networks and get RSSI values
  scanNetworks();;

  // Determine the room based on RSSI values

```

```

String currentRoom = determineRoom(rssi1, rssi2, rssi3);

// Log the room change only if it's different from the last
detected room
if (currentRoom != lastRoom) {
    logRoomChange(currentRoom); // Send room data to the serial
port for the Python script
    lastRoom = currentRoom; // Update the last detected room
}

delay(1000); // Wait for 1 second before the next loop
}

// Function to scan for networks and set the RSSI values
void scanNetworks() {
    int numNetworks = WiFi.scanNetworks();

    rssi1 = rssi2 = rssi3 = -100; // Initialize RSSI values to very
weak

    for (int i = 0; i < numNetworks; i++) {
        String ssid = WiFi.SSID(i);
        long rssi = WiFi.RSSI(i);

        // Match the SSID with the known access points and store their
RSSI values
        if (ssid == ssid1) {
            rssi1 = rssi;
        } else if (ssid == ssid2) {
            rssi2 = rssi;
        } else if (ssid == ssid3) {
            rssi3 = rssi;
        }
    }

    // Output RSSI values to Serial Monitor for debugging
    Serial.print("RSSI 1: ");
    Serial.println(rssi1);
    Serial.print("RSSI 2: ");
    Serial.println(rssi2);
    Serial.print("RSSI 3: ");
    Serial.println(rssi3);
}

// Function to determine which room the device is in
String determineRoom(long rssi1, long rssi2, long rssi3) {
    if (rssi1 > rssi2 && rssi1 > rssi3) {
        return "Room 1";
    } else if (rssi2 > rssi1 && rssi2 > rssi3) {
        return "Room 2";
    } else if (rssi3 > rssi1 && rssi3 > rssi2) {
        return "Room 3";
    } else {
        return "Between rooms";
    }
}

```

```

}
}

// Function to log the room change (sent to the Serial Monitor)
void logRoomChange(String room) {
    Serial.print("Room change detected: ");
    Serial.println(room);

    // Send the current room location to serial for the Python script
    Serial.print("Location: ");
    Serial.println(room);
}

```

Code 3 - Creating a database in Python (via IDLE)

```

import serial
import sqlite3
from datetime import datetime

# Open the serial connection to the Arduino (adjust 'COM12' to your
system's port)
ser = serial.Serial('COM12', 9600)
# Connect to the SQLite databases
location_conn = sqlite3.connect('location_history.db')
led_conn = sqlite3.connect('device_led_history.db')

location_cursor = location_conn.cursor()
led_cursor = led_conn.cursor()

# Create the LocationHistory table if it doesn't exist
location_cursor.execute('''
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS LocationHistory (
    id INTEGER PRIMARY KEY AUTOINCREMENT,
    location TEXT,
    timestamp DATETIME DEFAULT CURRENT_TIMESTAMP
)
''')
location_conn.commit()

# Create the DeviceLEDHistory table if it doesn't exist
led_cursor.execute('''
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS DeviceLEDHistory (
    id INTEGER PRIMARY KEY AUTOINCREMENT,
    led TEXT,
    state TEXT,
    timestamp DATETIME DEFAULT CURRENT_TIMESTAMP
)
''')
led_conn.commit()

```

```

# Infinite loop to constantly listen for data from the Arduino
try:
    while True:
        if ser.in_waiting > 0: # Check if there is data waiting from
the serial port
            line = ser.readline().decode('utf-8').strip() # Read and
decode the serial data

            # Check for room location updates
            if "Location:" in line:
                location = line.split(":")[1].strip() # Extract the
room location
                current_time = datetime.now().strftime('%Y-%m-%d
%H:%M:%S')

                # Insert the location and timestamp into the location
database
                location_cursor.execute("INSERT INTO LocationHistory
(location, timestamp) VALUES (?, ?)",
                                        (location, current_time))
                location_conn.commit()

                print(f "Logged Location: {location} at
{current_time}")

            # Check for LED state changes
            elif "Device turned" in line: # Matches "Device turned
ON/OFF"
                # Determine which LED (Green in this case) and its
new state
                if "Device turned ON" in line:
                    led = "Green"
                    state = "ON"
                elif "Device turned OFF" in line:
                    led = "Green"
                    state = "OFF"

                # Get the current timestamp
                led_time = datetime.now().strftime('%Y-%m-%d
%H:%M:%S')

                # Insert the LED state and timestamp into the LED
database
                led_cursor.execute("INSERT INTO DeviceLEDHistory
(led, state, timestamp) VALUES (?, ?, ?)",
                                    (led, state, led_time))
                led_conn.commit()

                print(f "Logged {led} LED state: {state} at
{led_time}")

            elif "Device needs repair" in line: # Matches the orange
LED state ON
                led = "Orange"

```

```

        state = "ON"

        # Get the current timestamp
        led_time = datetime.now().strftime('%Y-%m-%d
%H:%M:%S')

        # Insert the LED state and timestamp into the LED
database
        led_cursor.execute("INSERT INTO DeviceLEDHistory
(led, state, timestamp) VALUES (?, ?, ?)",
                            (led, state, led_time))
        led_conn.commit()

        print(f "Logged {led} LED state: {state} at
{led_time}")

    elif "Orange LED turned OFF" in line: # Matches the orange
LED state OFF
        led = "Orange"
        state = "OFF"

        # Get the current timestamp
        led_time = datetime.now().strftime('%Y-%m-%d
%H:%M:%S')

        # Insert the LED state and timestamp into the LED
database
        led_cursor.execute("INSERT INTO DeviceLEDHistory
(led, state, timestamp) VALUES (?, ?, ?)",
                            (led, state, led_time))
        led_conn.commit()

        print(f "Logged {led} LED state: {state} at
{led_time}")

except KeyboardInterrupt:
    print("Logging stopped.")

finally:
    # Cleanup: Close the serial connection and the database
connections
    ser.close()
    location_conn.close()
    led_conn.close()

```

Code 4 - Creating a server in Python (via IDLE)

```
import serial
import sqlite3
from flask import Flask, render_template, jsonify
from flask_socketio import SocketIO
from datetime import datetime
import threading

# Serial port configuration
ser = serial.Serial('COM12', 9600) # Replace 'COM12' with your
Arduino's port

# Flask-SocketIO setup
app = Flask(__name__)
socketio = SocketIO(app)

# Connect to SQLite databases
location_conn = sqlite3.connect('location_history.db',
check_same_thread=False)
led_conn = sqlite3.connect('device_led_history.db',
check_same_thread=False)

location_cursor = location_conn.cursor()
led_cursor = led_conn.cursor()

# Create the LocationHistory table if it doesn't exist
location_cursor.execute('''
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS LocationHistory (
    id INTEGER PRIMARY KEY AUTOINCREMENT,
    location TEXT,
    timestamp DATETIME DEFAULT CURRENT_TIMESTAMP
)
''')
location_conn.commit()

# Create the DeviceLEDHistory table if it doesn't exist
led_cursor.execute('''
CREATE TABLE IF NOT EXISTS DeviceLEDHistory (
    id INTEGER PRIMARY KEY AUTOINCREMENT,
    led TEXT,
    state TEXT,
    timestamp DATETIME DEFAULT CURRENT_TIMESTAMP
)
''')
led_conn.commit()

# Function to read serial data and update the database
def read_serial():
    while True:
        if ser.in_waiting > 0:
            line = ser.readline().decode('utf-8').strip()

            if "Location:" in line:
```

```

        location = line.split(":")[1].strip()
        current_time = datetime.now().strftime('%Y-%m-%d
%H:%M:%S')

        # Save to database
        location_cursor.execute("INSERT INTO LocationHistory
(location, timestamp) VALUES (?, ?)",
                               (location, current_time))
        location_conn.commit()

        # Emit to web app with current LED states
        socketio.emit('status_update', {'location': location,
'dot_blink': get_dot_blink(), 'led_state': get_led_state()})
        print(f "Logged Location: {location} at
{current_time}")

    elif "Device turned" in line:
        if "Device turned ON" in line:
            led = "Green"
            state = "ON"
        elif "Device turned OFF" in line:
            led = "Green"
            state = "OFF"

        led_time = datetime.now().strftime('%Y-%m-%d
%H:%M:%S')

        led_cursor.execute("INSERT INTO DeviceLEDHistory
(led, state, timestamp) VALUES (?, ?, ?)",
                           (led, state, led_time))
        led_conn.commit()

        # Emit to web app with current LED states
        socketio.emit('status_update', { 'location':
get_location(), 'dot_blink': get_dot_blink(), 'led_state': {'led':
led, 'state': state}}))
        print(f "Logged {led} LED state: {state} at
{led_time}")

    elif "Device needs repair" in line:
        led = "Orange"
        state = "ON"
        led_time = datetime.now().strftime('%Y-%m-%d
%H:%M:%S')

        led_cursor.execute("INSERT INTO DeviceLEDHistory
(led, state, timestamp) VALUES (?, ?, ?)",
                           (led, state, led_time))
        led_conn.commit()

        # Emit orange LED state change
        socketio.emit('status_update', { 'location':
get_location(), 'dot_blink': get_dot_blink(), 'led_state': {'led':
led, 'state': state}}))
        print(f "Logged {led} LED state: {state} at
{led_time}")

```

```

        elif "Orange LED turned OFF" in line:
            # Handle orange LED turning OFF
            led = "Orange"
            state = "OFF"

            # Save to database
            led_time = datetime.now().strftime('%Y-%m-%d
%H:%M:%S')
            led_cursor.execute("INSERT INTO DeviceLEDHistory
(led, state, timestamp) VALUES (?, ?, ?)",
                               (led, state, led_time))
            led_conn.commit()

            # Emit status update with new LED states
            socketio.emit('status_update', { 'location':
get_location(), 'dot_blink': get_dot_blink(), 'led_state': {'led':
led, 'state': state}}))
            print(f "Logged {led} LED state: {state} at
{led_time}")

# Flask routes
@app.route('/')
def index():
    return render_template('index.html')

@app.route('/api/status')
def status():
    """
    Returns the current location and LED states with priority logic
for the orange LED.
    """
    led_state = get_led_state()
    dot_blink = False # Default: dot does not blink

    if led_state: # Check if any LED state exists
        if led_state["led"] == "Orange" and led_state["state"] ==
"ON":
            dot_blink = True # Orange LED overrides everything
        elif led_state["led"] == "Green" and led_state["state"] ==
"ON":
            dot_blink = False # Green LED doesn't make the dot blink

    # Send location and blink state to the frontend
    return jsonify(location=get_location(), dot_blink=dot_blink,
led_state=led_state)

# Helper functions to query the database
def get_location():
    location_cursor.execute("SELECT location FROM LocationHistory
ORDER BY id DESC LIMIT 1")
    result = location_cursor.fetchone()
    return result[0] if result else None

```

```

def get_led_state():
    """ Returns the last recorded LED state as a dictionary. """
    led_cursor.execute("SELECT led, state FROM DeviceLEDHistory ORDER
BY id DESC LIMIT 1")
    result = led_cursor.fetchone()
    return {"led": result[0], "state": result[1]} if result else None

def get_dot_blink():
    """
    Determines whether the dot should blink based on LED states.
    Priority: Orange LED overrides Green LED.
    """
    led_state = get_led_state()
    if led_state:
        if led_state["led"] == "Orange" and led_state["state"] ==
"ON":
            return True # Blink if Orange is ON
        elif led_state["led"] == "Green" and led_state["state"] ==
"ON":
            return False # No blink for Green LED
        else:
            return False # Default for other states (both OFF)
    return False # Default to no blink if no state found

@socketio.on('connect')
def handle_connect():
    print("Client connected")

    # Emit initial status upon connection with correct initial states
for LEDs and blinking.
    socketio.emit('status_update', {
        'location': get_location(),
        'dot_blink': get_dot_blink(),
        'led_state': get_led_state()
    })

if __name__ == '__main__':
    threading.Thread(target=read_serial, daemon=True).start() # Run
serial reader in a separate thread
    socketio.run(app, host='0.0.0.0', port=5000)

```

Code 5 - Create a web page in Visual Studio Code

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="en">
<head>
  <meta charset="UTF-8">
  <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-
scale=1.0">
  <title>Arduino Location Tracker</title>.
  <link rel="stylesheet" href="/static/styles.css">
  <style>
    .floor-plan {
      position: relative;
      width: 800px; /* Adjust based on your floor plan image
dimensions */
      height: 600px;
      background-image: url('/static/floor_plan.png');;
      background-size: contain;
      background-repeat: no-repeat;
    }
    .dot {
      position: absolute;
      width: 30px;
      height: 30px;
      border-radius: 50%;
      background-color: red; /* Default state: Red when both
LEDs are OFF */
      transition: top 0.3s ease, left 0.3s ease, background-
color 0.3s ease;
    }
    .repair-message {
      position: absolute;
      top: 50%;
      left: 35%;
      transform: translate(-50%, -50%);
      font-size: 24px;
      font-weight: bold;
      color: red;
      background: rgba(255, 255, 255, 0.8);
      padding: 10px 20px;
      border-radius: 10px;
      border: 2px solid red;
      display: none; /* Initially hidden */
      z-index: 10;
      text-align: center;
    }
  </style>
</head>
<body>
  <h1>Arduino Location and LED Status</h1>
  <div class="floor-plan" id="floor-plan">
    <div class="dot" id="dot"></div>
    <div class="repair-message" id="repair-message">Device needs
repair</div>
```

```

</div>

<script
src="https://cdn.socket.io/4.5.0/socket.io.min.js"></script>

<script>
  document.addEventListener('DOMContentLoaded', () => {
    const socket = io(); // Connect to the Flask-SocketIO
server

    const dot = document.getElementById('dot');
    const repairMessage = document.getElementById('repair-
message'); // Repair message element

    // Define positions for each room
    const roomPositions = {
      "Room 1": { top: "400px", left: "120px" },
      "Room 2": { top: "225px", left: "120px" },
      "Room 3": { top: "225px", left: "500px" },
    };

    let blinkInterval = null; // To manage blinking interval
    let orangeBlinking = false; // Flag to indicate if orange
LED is blinking

    // Function to start blinking the dot in orange
    function startOrangeBlinking() {
      if (!orangeBlinking) {
        orangeBlinking = true;
        let visible = true;
        blinkInterval = setInterval(() => {
          dot.style.backgroundColor = visible ?
"orange" : "transparent";
          visible = !visible;
        }, 500); // Blink every 500ms

        repairMessage.style.display = "block"; // Show
the repair message
      }
    }

    // Function to stop blinking
    function stopBlinking() {
      if (blinkInterval) {
        clearInterval(blinkInterval);
        blinkInterval = null;
        orangeBlinking = false;
        dot.style.backgroundColor = "red"; // Reset to red
when blinking stops
        repairMessage.style.display = "none"; // Hide the
repair message
      }
    }

    // Listen for status updates from the server

```

```

        socket.on('status_update', (data) => {
            console.log('Received status_update:', data); //
Debugging log

            const { location, led_state } = data;

            // Update dot position based on room location received
from server
            if (roomPositions[location]) {
                dot.style.top = roomPositions[location].top;
                dot.style.left = roomPositions[location].left;
            }

            // Handle LED states and dot color logic
            if (led_state) {
                const isGreenOn = led_state.led === "Green" &&
led_state.state === "ON";
                const isOrangeOn = led_state.led === "Orange" &&
led_state.state === "ON";

                // Prioritize orange LED: if orange LED is ON,
start blinking and ignore green LED
                if (isOrangeOn) {
                    console.log('Orange LED is ON, starting
blink...');;

                    startOrangeBlinking();
                } else {
                    stopBlinking(); // Stop blinking if orange is
OFF

                    // Handle green LED state if orange LED is OFF
                    if (isGreenOn) {
                        console.log('Green LED is ON and Orange
LED is OFF, setting dot to green...');;
                        dot.style.backgroundColor = "green";
                    } else {
                        console.log('Both LEDs are OFF or only
green is OFF, setting dot to red...');;
                        dot.style.backgroundColor = "red";
                    }
                }
            } else {
                stopBlinking(); // Ensure no blinking when no
conditions are met

                dot.style.backgroundColor = "red"; // Default
state when both LEDs are OFF
            }
        });
    });
</script>
</body>
</html>

```

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